

NORMS OF FERTILIZING PUMPKINS WITH MIXED FERTILIZERS

Bayniyazova Marziya Azhniyazovna

A master student of the specialty "Agrochemistry", Karakalpakstan Institute of
Agriculture and Agrotechnologies

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Abstract. Pumpkin is one of the most popular gourds in the agriculture. It is considered as unpretentious and undemanding to care. The taste and volume of the crop largely depend on the quality of the soil. And in order to grow large tasty fruits, the pumpkin needs proper fertilizing during flowering and fruiting. Therefore, the article deals with the norms of fertilizing pumpkins with mixed fertilizers.

Keywords: agriculture, pumpkin, to fertilize, fertilizers, norms, soil, nutrients, harvest.

Introduction. Pumpkin needs a large supply of nutrients to grow and bear fruit, so it is advisable to grow it on fertile soil. The soil must be fertilized before planting, continuing to fertilize throughout the growing season. When choosing how to feed a pumpkin in the open field, there is a need to take into account the preferences of the culture. In order for the pumpkin to grow well and give a bountiful harvest, the soil must contain plenty of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and calcium [5, 67-70]. The roots of a pumpkin can go into the soil by 2 meters, the ripening period of the berry is up to 140 days, so the plant greatly impoverishes the earth, literally sucking all the juices out of it. Therefore, the beds where the pumpkin grows need to be fertilized regularly.

Timing of fertilizer application. Pumpkin feeding is carried out at a certain time. If the soil is fertile, it is enough to use fertilizers only three times per season. Depleted soils will have to be fed once every 2 weeks. Some signs indicate that an extraordinary top dressing for a pumpkin is required: seedlings grow poorly from the moment of transplantation; leaves curl, turn yellow and fall off; the back of the leaves turns purple; fruits are poorly tied; flowering slows down [3, 93-95].

The first fertilizer is applied when 4-5 leaves are formed. The second time feeding will be needed at the growth stage of the lashes. Fertilizer seedlings are carried out according to the following scheme: 10 days after germination of sprouts. 5 days before landing in an open area. 14 days after landing in the ground. When will the first lashes appear. These dates may vary depending on the growing conditions and the condition of the seedlings. The last time pumpkin fertilizer is applied at the end of summer, before harvest.

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To maintain growth and development, organic or mineral fertilizers for pumpkins are used, as well as folk remedies. The culture needs nitrogen, potassium and phosphorus. The first is applied at the beginning of the growing season, the second and third - when flowers are tied and fruits are formed [1, 43-48].

Mineral fertilizers that can be used to feed pumpkins in an open field care scheme: 10 g of urea per 1 bucket of water; a mixture of 20 g of superphosphates, 15 g of potassium sulfate and 20 g of ammofoska in a bucket of water. a solution of 15 g of superphosphate and 10 g of potassium sulfate in 12 liters of water. The most popular among industrial fats are the drugs "Juno", "Kemira", "Universal". They are a ready-made mixture of nitrogen, phosphorus and potash fertilizers in the right dosage.

Organic fertilizers- before planting in the ground, the soil is fertilized with wood ash. It will give the plant strength to grow and protect against pests. For each hole take 1 tbsp powder. In the second half of the growing season, a solution of 200 g of ash and a bucket of water is used as a fertilizer. The liquid is insisted for three days, and then the beds are watered with it. It is used other available organic top dressings: slurry diluted with water in a ratio of 1:10; chicken manure, after diluting the raw materials with water in a ratio of 1:20. For each bush you will need 2 liters of this or that solution, and during fruit ripening - 3 liters.

Conclusion. According to the presented data, it can be concluded that the usage of mixed fertilizers to pumpkin is beneficial for growth and development of pumpkins. The presented norms for fertilizing pumpkins are recommended for the usage of fertilizing pumpkins in the agriculture.

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